

EFFECT OF REMITTANCES ON SOCIO-ECONOMIC FACTORS OF HOUSEHOLDS IN DISTRICT MOHMAND, KHYBER PAKHTUNKHWA, PAKISTAN

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Abstract

Remittance is one of the key indicators for the development of any developing country like Pakistan. This study investigated what socio-economic factors affect remittances in district Mohmand Khyber Pakhtunkhwa. Simple random sampling technique for selection of sample was used through Krejcie and Morgan formula. The current study mainly based on primary data and used a standard questionnaire. The data was collected from 162 sample household heads in the study area. In this study simple linear regression model was used for the analysis. The study has used two dependent variables such as education expenses and consumption expenses and one independent variable, which were remittances of households. The results of the regression model indicates that education expenses has positive and significant relationship with remittances and consumption expenses has also found positive and significant relationship with remittances in the study area. It concluded from the current study that the education expenses and consumption expenses are the main factors and it mainly focused and depend on remittances, especially in district Mohmand. The study suggested that foreign remittances improve the socio-economic situation and decision making of households, but spending habits do not prioritize investment, Instead of focusing on opulent household equipment. It is recommended that the households of district Mohmand make better use of their limited resources and invest in both long and short term opportunities.

INTRODUCTION

Remittances are money and items sent to homes by migrant workers who employees outside of their home community (Adams and Cuecuecha 2010). They have grown significantly in recent years and now contribute to the majority of foreign revenue in many emerging economies, playing a key role in their economic and social growth. As reported by the World Bank, remittances to countries with low or middle incomes (LMICs) increased by 5% to \$626 billion in 2022, despite global economic difficulties.

This figure is significantly lower than the 10.2% growth in 2021. Remittances are an important source of household income in low- and middle-income countries. They reduce poverty, enhance nutritional outcomes, and are linked to greater birth weight and school enrolment rates for disadvantaged children (World Bank, 2020).

There are around 250 million migrant workers world wide who send remittances to their home countries reaching more than \$500 billion each year.

The number of people working abroad, notably in Gulf nations, has gradually increased in recent years, and their families rely largely on the money they bring home. The standard of life in society is growing for a variety of reasons. These elements are critical in a certain civilization. Remittances from overseas, which indicate the flow of cash into poor countries, are one of these factors. According to Combes and Ebeke (2011), remittance inflows minimize household consumption volatility since the surplus capacity to spend helps them to maintain current consumption. There is a strong correlation between migration and consumption behavior. Migration might be viewed as an option for improving consumption habits. Migration with earned income, such as remittances, also contributes to higher consumption, at least in the migrants' home countries. Evidence from earlier literature is inconsistent. It demonstrates that remittances can affect education in a positive or negative way. Remittances provided by immigrants to their families are a plus since they loosen credit restrictions and stimulate spending on children's education. Remittances assist in enrolling children who are not currently enrolled in any educational institution owing to credit restrictions as well as extending the time that they are now enrolled in school. Another factor is that an individual's return to education is higher while migrating overseas if there is a high potential for highly educated and skilled labor migration. So, it has a favorable impact on children's academic achievement. Alternately, if there are many opportunities for migration for low-skilled and unskilled labor, return to education are lower, which has a negative impact on migrant households' children's school attendance and achievement (Chaaban and Mansaur, 2012). Household spending on consumption is a significant component of the gross domestic product (GDP). All types of consumption account for around two-thirds of the total gross domestic GDP (Mankiw, 2019). In poor nations, this ratio exceeds two-thirds of the total gross domestic GDP. For example, Pakistan's consumer expenditure-to-GDP ratio in 2020 was 82% (World Bank, 2020). Remittance flows, which are an essential component of development funding, were reasonably high during the 2008 financial crisis and the 2014 Ebola outbreak. Nonetheless, the globe

is currently in peril due to the COVID-19 epidemic. In 2020, remittance flows to low and middle-income countries are expected to fall by 19.7% to USD 445 billion, possibly the greatest reduction in history (World Bank). According to the World Bank, this decline is mostly due to the financial crisis caused by the COVID-19 epidemic; for migratory workers, the pandemic has resulted in a drop in profits and business. Lockdown estimates implemented in host countries have resulted in countless migrants losing their employment, reducing remittance flows to emerging countries.

Remittances play an important role in the development of Pakistan. It improve standard of living, alleviate poverty, boost wellbeing, while providing countries with foreign currency to pay for vital imports and service external debt. As a result, access to foreign finance markets improves. In District Mohmand the sampled population Shah Alam Salay, Sherano kali, Zareef kor villages face a lot of problem related to Education and consumption expenditure. Majority of population living in District Mohmand are not highly educated and poor therefore, they migrated to abroad as a labor as a result they sent money to home country. They depend on remittances because they have not any proper source of income. Therefore, the current study seeks to contribute to the existing literature on the uses of remittances at destination by focusing on the influence of remittances on household investment decisions concerning children's education and consumer expenditure.

Yousafzai (2015) investigates the impact of overseas remittances on Pakistani families' spending habits using the Household Income and Expenditure Survey (HIES). He 13 finds that non-remittance recipient families spend more on food and less on physical and human capital, whereas beneficiary households spend more on physical and human capital. The study's findings also support the persistent income hypothesis of consumption.

Cuadros, M and Gaduh (2017) studied the effects of foreign remittances as a secondary Means for revenue on the decision in Columbia between child labor and education. The findings showed that a one-unit increase in remittances increased the likelihood of attending school. Similar to this, child labor is an example of an inverse circumstance.

Hines and Simpson (2019) studied that there is a relationship between remittances received and household allocation patterns. The study's major result is that increased remittances boost educational investment in Kenya.

Ahmad et al (2019) studied the foreign remittances and human resource development in developing countries. The study used a panel data set of 151 developing nations from 1990 to 2016 in order to give a comprehensive understanding of the link between foreign remittances and development of human resources in developing economies. The World Bank's World Development Indicators were utilized to obtain the data. HRD is quantified by indirect measures such as newborn mortality rate (for health) and secondary school enrollment (for education). The results of the Generalized Method of Moments (GMM) approach show how remittances

contribute to the growth of HRD. According to dis aggregated estimates based on economies' per capita GNP, remittances had a stronger impact on decreasing infant mortality in high-income countries and increasing school attendance in low-income countries. Remittances have an impact in a variety of ways, according to dis aggregate assessment based on the regional classification of economies. The current study determined what socio-economic factors of households affect the remittances in the study area.

Hypotheses of the Study

H₁: There is significant effect of remittances on education.

H₂: There is significant effect of remittances on consumption expenditure.

Conceptual Framework

Materials and Methods

This section of the study describes the techniques and tools which are used to carry out the research. It has consists of the Population of the study, Sampling techniques and sample size of the study, Data Collection and Econometrics model of the study. All of these have been briefly given below.

Population of the Study

In order to conduct an in-depth analysis, questionnaire surveys were used to collect primary data for the underlying study from randomly selected households. The study was conducted in District Mohmand which is located in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa. Majority of its people largely depends on foreign remittances to fulfill their basic necessities of life. Therefore, the population of the study is Tehsil Ekka Ghund Villages from District Mohmand.

Sample & Sampling design

The current study is mainly based on primary data which have been collected through standard questionnaire. It has has used simple random sampling technique for selecting sample from the population through Krejcie and Morgan Formula.

$$n = \frac{\chi^2 NP(1 - P)}{d^2(N - 1) + \chi^2 P(1 - P)}$$

Where χ^2 is the chi square value corresponding to 95% confidence interval (3.8416), N represents the given population size (280), P is the population proportion (0.50) and (d) refers to margin of error or degree of accuracy (0.05) at 95% confidence interval. Using the above mentioned formula, the required sample size for this study has 162.

Table 3.1 Distribution of the Sample Respondent in the study Area

Name Of villages	Total population	Sample size
Shah Alam Salay	87	50
Sheerano Kali	90	55
Zareef Kor	103	57
Total	280	162

Source: Primary data collected of Tehsil Ekka Ghund from 2023 survey

Econometric Model

In this study Simple Regression Model were used because there is a single independent variable and one dependent variable. It is given below:

$$Y_i = \beta_0 + \beta_i X_i + \epsilon_i \dots\dots\dots eq (1)$$

Data analysis Procedure

The data have been analyzed using the most recent version of SPSS 17 software. The study has two dependent variables and one independent variable. The dependent variables have been Households education and household’s consumption. Where household’s education refers to the ongoing education process of the members of the family on the other hand household consumption refers to the consumption activities of the households in the study area. The independent variable has been remittances in Rupees which refer to money sent by the people working aboard to their family. The study has used linear regression model in which each explanatory variable has individually regressed on dependent variable.

Model-1

$$Education = \beta_0 + \beta_i \text{ Remittances in Rupees} \dots\dots\dots eq (2)$$

Specification of the model

Y = Education of the Households in years.

β_0 = Intercept of the model

β_i = Parameters of the model.

X_1 = Remittances in Rupees.

ϵ_i = Error term.

Model-2

$$Consumption expenditures = \beta_0 + \beta_i \text{ Remittances in Rupees} + \epsilon_i \dots\dots\dots eq (3)$$

Specification of the model

Y = Consumption expenditure of the Households in years.

β_0 = Intercept of the model.

β_i = Parameters of the model.

X_1 = remittances in Rupees.

ϵ_i = Error term.

Diagnostic test

Diagnostic test is concerned with determining the sensitivity and specificity of various diagnostic tests, as well as their predictive values and other metrics of relevance. Normality has been checked. A normality test analyzes if a sample of data comes from a normally distributed population. It is often conducted to test if the data used in the study has a normal distribution.

Results and Discussions

In this section of the study explained the results and discussion regarding the study variables. The study has analyzed two simple linear regression models. It included the results of normality tests and coefficients of regression models. This study based on primary survey, which collected through questionnaire.

4.1 Estimated Results of Kolmogorov-Smirnov and Shapiro-Wilk Tests for Education Expenses

Table 4.1 indicates the results of normality tests of Shapiro-Wilk and Kolmogorov-Smirnov. Normality is one of the assumptions of regression model. The value of Shapiro-Wilk and Kolmogorov-Smirnov test is greater than 0.05, it shows normality and when it is less than 0.05, it indicate non normality. In table 4.1 the results of both test are greater than 0.05, which is 0.210 and 0.060 respectively, so this is the evidence that data has normality distributed and follow the regression model assumption.

Table 4.1 Result of Normality Tests for Education Expenses

	Kolmogorov-Smirnov			Shapiro-Wilk		
	Statistic	Df	Sig.	Statistic	df	Sig.
Education Expenses (in Rupees)	0.327	162	0.060	0.367	162	0.210

Source: Primary Survey (2024)

4.2 Estimated Coefficients of Simple Regression Model

Table 4.2 shows the results of estimated coefficients of simple linear regression model for the education expenses. In this study two simple linear regression models were analyzed. The first one was used for education expenses as a dependent variable and second one was used for consumption expenses as a dependent variable in the study area. The value of coefficient of correlation (R) is 0.622 which explained that there is a positive and strong association between education expenses and monthly remittances. The value of goodness of fit test is 0.387, which indicates that 39 percent variations in education expenses due to monthly remittances of households in the study area. The adjusted R² value is 0.383, which is the

modify form of R². The F test shows the overall significance of the model. Its value is 100.8 which are greater than 4, so the overall model is significant. Moreover, the table 4.2 shows the coefficient of monthly remittances in rupees of households in the study area. The coefficient value of monthly remittances is 0.109. It's explained that one rupee increase in monthly remittances of households their education expenses has increased by 0.109 percent. The relationship between education expenses and monthly remittances has found positive and significant. Amuedo-Dorantes & Pozo (2006), Yang (2008), and Nasir et al (2011) studied relationship between education and remittances were positive and significant and results of the study also show positive and significant relationship between education expenses and monthly remittances.

Table 4.2 Estimated Coefficients of Simple Regression Model for Education Expenses

	Unstandardized Coefficients		t	Sig.
	β	Std. Error		
Constant	32743.09	13494.26	2.426	0.016
Monthly Remittances (in Rupees)	0.109	0.011	10.043	0.000

Source: Primary Survey (2024) R = 0.622 R² = 0.387 Adj R² = 0.383 F_{test} = 100.8

Dependent Variable: Education Expenses

4.3 Estimated Results of Kolmogorov-Smirnov and Shapiro-Wilk Tests for Consumption Expenses

Table 4.3 shows that the results of normality tests of Shapiro-Wilk and Kolmogorov-Smirnov. Normality is one of the assumptions of regression model. The value of Shapiro-Wilk and Kolmogorov-Smirnov test

is greater than 0.05, it shows normality and when it is less than 0.05, it indicate that the data is not normally distributed . In table 4.3 the results of both test are greater than 0.05, which is 0.062 and 0.080 respectively, so this is the evidence that data has normally distributed and follow the regression model assumption.

Table 4.3 Estimated Results of Shapiro-Wilk and Kolmogorov-Smirnov for Normality

	Kolmogorov-Smirnov			Shapiro-Wilk		
	Statistic	Df	Sig.	Statistic	df	Sig.
Consumption Expenses (in Rupees)	0.290	162	0.080	0.360	162	0.062

Source: Primary Survey (2024)

4.4 Estimated Coefficients of Simple Regression Model f Monthly Remittances

Table 4.4 shows the results of estimated coefficients of simple linear regression model for the consumption expenses. In this model monthly remittance as an independent variable and consumption expenses as a dependent variable of households were analyzed. The result indicates that the value of coefficient of correlation (R) is 0.719; it explained that there is a positive and strong association between consumption expenses and monthly remittances. It means that when monthly remittances increase the consumption expenses also increases by 72 percent. The concerned table also shows the value of coefficient of determination, which is 0.518, which indicates that 52 percent explained the consumption expenses by monthly remittances of households in the study area. The

adjusted R² value is 0.515, which is the modify form of R². The F test shows the overall significance of the model. In this model its value is 171.7 which are greater than 4, so this is the evidence that the overall model is significant. Moreover, the table 4.4 indicates the coefficient of monthly remittances in rupees of households in the study area. The coefficient value of monthly remittances is 0.273. The value explained that one rupee increase in monthly remittances of households their consumption expenses has increased by 0.273 percent. Yousafzai (2015) investigates the impact of overseas remittances on Pakistani families' spending and found that beneficiary households spend more on physical and human capital Table 4.4 demonstrates that the relationship between consumption expenses and monthly remittances has found positive and significant.

Table 4.4 Estimated Coefficients of Simple Regression Model for Consumption Expenses

	Unstandardized Coefficients		t	Sig.
	β	Std. Error		
(Constant)	116814.842	25831.932	4.522	0.000
Monthly Remittances (in Rupees)	0.273	0.021	13.104	0.000

Source: Primary Survey (2024) R = 0.719 R² = 0.518 Adj R² = 0.515 F_{test} = 171.7
 Dependent Variable: Consumption Expenses

Conclusion

Remittances play an important role in the development of Pakistan. It improve standard of living, alleviate poverty, boost wellbeing, while providing countries with foreign currency to pay for vital imports and service external debt. As a result, access to foreign finance markets improves.

Majority of population living in District Mohmand are not highly educated and poor therefore, they migrated to abroad as a labor as a result they sent money to home country. They depend on remittances because they have not any proper source of income. The main objective of the study is to investigate that what socio economic factors affect remittances in the study area. After applying different models the study shows that remittances effect education and consumption of households. In this study two simple linear regression models were analyzed. The first one was used for education expenses as a dependent variable and second one was used for consumption expenses as a dependent variable in the study area. Normality tests of Shapiro-Wilk and Kolmogorov-Smirnov were used. Normality is one of the assumptions of regression model. The value of Shapiro-Wilk and Kolmogorov-Smirnov test is greater than 0.05, it shows normality and when it is less than 0.05, it indicate non normality. In table 4.1 the results of both test are greater than 0.05, which is 0.210 and 0.060 respectively, so this is the evidence that data has normality distributed and follow the regression model assumption. The value of coefficient of correlation (R) is 0.622 which explained that there is a positive and strong association between education expenses and monthly remittances. The F test shows the overall significance of the model. Its value is 100.8 which are greater than 4, so the overall model is significant. The result indicates that the value of coefficient of correlation (R) is 0.719; it explained that there is a positive and strong association between consumption expenses and monthly remittances. The F test shows the overall significance of the model. In this model its value is 171.7 which are greater than 4, so this is the evidence that the overall model is significant.

Recommendations

- Although foreign remittances improve the socio-economic situations and decision-making of households, but their spending habits do not prioritize investment, instead focusing on opulent household equipment. It is advised that the households of District Mohmand make better use of their limited resources and invest in both long and short-term opportunities.
 - People of District Mohmand tend to send their children overseas for financial advantages rather than for higher education.
 - Government and NGO'S programs should educate these families on finding sustainable domestic revenue to support them over time.
- Most of the people in the study area have limited access to better job prospects and appealing nations. Policymakers should develop measures to educate them.

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